

ELDER TREE (*Sambucus*) AS AN AID TO REDUCE CORONAVIRUS VIRAL LOAD

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ABSTRACT

Hemagglutinin is a biological response where glycoproteins cause erythrocytes to agglutinate, or clump together; this response helps host infection, contributing highly to virulence, in other words a virus binds to cells and infects them as an attachment factor. There are over 15 types of hemagglutinin (H), H1, H2, H3 ... and several types of neuraminidase (N). N1, N2, N3... therefore a common human virus of influenza A can be divided into: subtypes, clades and sub-clades. One example of influenza type A is A (H1N1).

Highly pathogenic avian influenza viruses have highly basic furin cleavage sites at the hemagglutinin protein HA1-HA2 interface allowing maturation of virions and more efficient viral replication. The RRAR insertion in SARS-CoV-2 might serve a similar function. The protein sequence of the S glycoprotein of SARS-CoV-2 shows the presence of a furin cleavage sequence (PRRARS|V).

ELDER TREE (*Sambucus*) AS A HEMAGGLUTININ INHIBITOR

Hippocrates referred to the elder tree as "medicine chest." Known for centuries Elder tree has been used in folk medicine for the treatment of colds, flu and herpes infections.

Dr Martin Blochwich described the benefits back in 1644. In recent years, preliminary evidence through (DART TOF-MS) indicates that Elderberry has strong antiviral activity by neutralizing hemagglutinin spikes on the surface of viruses, those compounds found in previous researches were identified as: **5,7,3',4'-tetra-O-methylquercetin** and **5,7-dihydroxy-4-oxo-2-(3,4,5-trihydroxyphenyl) chroman-3-yl-3,4,5-trihydroxycyclohexanecarboxylate**, however These findings need to be confirmed in a larger study.

According to several in vitro studies, coronaviruses have seven major targets: spike protein, envelop protein, membrane, protein protease, nucleocapsid protein, hemagglutinin esterase, and helicase, among several other protein structures, it is important to mention that **hemagglutinin, esterase** mediates reversible attachment to **O-acetylated-sialic-acids** by acting both as **lectins** and as receptor-destroying enzymes. Related HEs occur in coronaviruses, as a result of relatively recent lateral gene transfer events.

Viruses that have hemagglutinin activity (HA) **glycoproteins** on their surfaces bind to **N-Acetylneuraminic acid (Neu5Ac or NANA)** sialic acid found on the surface of human erythrocytes and on the cell membranes of the upper respiratory tract. This is the basis of hemagglutination when viruses are mixed with blood cells, and entry of the virus into cells of the upper respiratory tract. Two examples are oseltamivir and zanamivir sialic acid analogs that interfere with release of newly generated viruses from infected cells by inhibiting sialidases responsible for mobility of virus particles through the respiratory tract mucus stopping the virus from spreading.

Lectins from elderberry have been found to bind to **Neu5Acalpha2,6Gal/GalNAc**, studies have shown that three amino-acid residues, **S(197)**, **A(233)** and **Q(234)**, in the C-terminal subdomain of **SSA-B** chain are critical for the binding to the sialic acid in **Neu5Acalpha2,6Gal/GalNAc** sequence. Although not completely understood, Elder tree has proved to somehow reduce the viral load by inhibiting binding of the virus into healthy cells and more extensive research will be needed in order to understand the whole process on how some plants can stop viruses from infecting healthy cells.

KEYWORDS

Hemagglutinin, Neu5Acalpha2,6Gal/GalNAc, coronavirus, Elder tree, Sambucus, 5,7,3',4'-tetra-O-methylquercetin, chroman-3-yl-3,4,5-trihydroxycyclohexanecarboxylate, H1N1, influenza, SARS-CoV-2, spike protein, envelop protein, membrane, protein protease, nucleocapsid protein, hemagglutinin esterase, helicase, Covid, oseltamivir, Natural remedy, sialic acid, herbal medicine.